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The Effect of Work Ethics of Employees on their Work Performance

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ABSTRACT

Employees with strong work ethics present themselves as professionals in every sense of the word. The study determined the effect of the work ethics of employees on their work performance. The literature review was undertaken to deepen the concept and establish the theories of the study. Descriptive assessment and correlational research design were applied. It used research questionnaires to gather the data from the respondents consisting of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag. The study found that the work ethics of employees along three components (the attitude toward the work itself, moral attitude toward the work, and intrinsic motivation) are considered high. Their work performance along with task and contextual performance is high, while counterproductive behavior is low. In terms of the correlation between work ethics and individual work performance, the results manifested a significant correlation between work ethics and individual work performance. But taking the dimensions of work ethics separately, only the attitude toward the work itself and intrinsic motivation affect the individual work performance along with task and contextual performance. Moreover, a moral attitude toward the work affects counterproductive behavior.

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Introduction

Employees must be equipped with the right values and work behavior considering the importance of the organization's strategic direction and financial capital to support the implementation of the vision and mission. Work ethics of employees are given priority because they can affect the effectiveness and performance of the organization. This is proven by many studies like that of Salahudin, et al (2016), Osibanjo, et al (2015), Bataineh (2020), Benedicto and Caelian (2021), and Banister (2017). All these researches suggest that management needs to establish policies and practices that guide the employee's work behavior. Failing to inculcate the right work values in the employees can greatly affect the organization's productivity and performance.

Issues on work ethics encompass all kinds of organizations (Painter, 2006). Many issues of corruption have been linked to the absence of work ethics (Whitton, 2021, Tasi & Syamsir, 2021). In addressing such an issue, Whitton

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(2021) in Transparency International suggests some guidelines to prevent corruption such as: **anticipating** specific threats to ethics standards and integrity in the public sector, strengthening the ethical competence of civil servants, strengthening mechanisms to support professional ethics, and developing administrative practices and processes which promote ethical values and integrity. It is the same story with the bankruptcies in private corporations which have been associated with work ethics (Tamari, 1990). The negative effect of work ethics problems is the organization's inability to improve social services that promote the welfare of the general public and the inability to provide quality services to its stakeholder, which leads to its bankruptcy.

Slow progress has also been associated with work ethics (Sunday & Michael, 2018). When employees have no proper work ethics or right attitude toward their work, this can affect their performance (Salahudin, et al (2016), Osibanjo, et al (2015). Based on their findings, the researcher was motivated to find out the work ethics of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag. It identified their work ethics issues and provided evidence-based information for the management to create policies and practices for improvement. It is noteworthy that there have been no studies conducted to investigate this problem.

The study consists of five parts. The first part is the introduction, which explains the study's rationale and purpose. The second part is the literature review that presents theories of the study based on the existing literature and studies. This is to deepen the understanding of the study and establish the theories of the study. The third part is the research methodology which presents the research design, population, locale of the study, research instruments, data gathering procedures, ethical procedures, and the statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the data presentation and analysis which presents data statistically and is followed by interpretation and analysis. The fifth part is the result and discussion of the result and implications.

Literature Review

The objective of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the concept of the study based on the existing literature and studies and establish the theories as the basis for the investigation.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Clarifying the Concept of Ethics and Morality

Ethics has been confused with morality and people often use the terms interchangeably (Grannan, n.d, Articulo, 2004). Both have slightly different meanings, but they are closely related as they both refer to ethical judgment or ethical principles. Tracing the root word of ethics comes from the Greek word, "ethos" which means moral character, habitual character, and disposition, habit, customs, manners, and the Latin word for ethics is "mos" (genitivoreors) and in plural form is "mores" which means customs, precepts, law, rule, conduct, behavior, character, manners, and morals/ethics. Looking at these original words of ethics and meanings from Greek and Latin words shows that the concerns of both "ethos" and "mores" are what is morally good and bad and morally right and wrong (Singer, 2022). It appears that the confusion about the word "ethics and morality" originated from the Latin word which influenced people to use the two terms interchangeably. Ordinary people use the terms to mean the same thing: the way how individuals choose to interact with one another (Cornel Law School, 1992). It defines what morally good and bad are

for the individual, society, and the nature of duties that people owe themselves (Cornel Law School, 1992). The Latin word, “mores” develops the term “moral” or morality which refers to the code of conduct or specific rules of conduct or behavior put forward by the society, the group, the individual, or rational persons (Gert, & Gert, 2011). However, in the development of the discussions of ethics, some philosophers have presented the idea about their difference. On one hand, a group of philosophers uses the term “ethics” as the moral philosophy that deals with the morality of a certain act or the standards to determine the morality of a certain act (Singer, 2022). It deals with the question of why a certain act or behavior is good or bad, or in short, it is the study or science of morals. While morality refers to the code of conduct or moral norms. On the other hand, many philosophers also use the two terms. The original concept of ethics (*ethos*) and morality (*Latin word: mores*) to mean the same thing was used in this study. This refers to moral character, moral behavior, manner, and customs, hence using the term interchangeably was expected.

The history of ethics or morality is concerned with what is morally good and bad, morally right and wrong (Singer, 2022). It came into existence when human beings lived in a community, group, or society. Different groups, society, and cultures establish their moral conduct to guide the behavior on how to relate to and deal with others (Singer, 2022). It answers the question of “how should I live?” or “how should I behave”? These questions suggest that ethics or morality is not only about an individual moral guide for oneself but it is also an individual’s guide on how to relate to or deal with other people. Thus, society provides the standard code of moral behavior/conduct. These rules should be accepted by society, the group, and the individual, and even by all rational agents who have reason and free will (Gert & Gert, 2011).

The purpose of morality or ethics is not only for one’s happiness but also for the harmony and happiness of the great majority of people. Pojman (2000) explains that morality has five purposes: “to keep society from falling apart”, “to ameliorate human suffering”, “to promote human suffering”, and “to resolve conflict of interest in just and orderly ways”, and “to assign praise and blame, reward the good and punish the guilty”. According to him, these are the five conditions to meet if a certain act is considered moral or immoral. This suggests that any act committed by any rational agent is morally right if it is accepted by the society where the person is living (relativism) (Ladd, 1973) or if it is accepted by all rational agents (Universal morality) (Acton, 1970).

Morality or ethics becomes an individual’s guide on how to make morally good and right decisions that will affect a group or society. Either one makes the decision based on the consequence of actions for the greatest majority of people, and not for self-interest (utilitarianism) (Mack, 1962, Sen & Williams, 1982). Further, one can make a decision based on the universal law which states that you can only perform a certain action if you allow others to do the same under the same circumstance (Universalism) (Kant as cited by O’Neill (1975, 1989, Rawls, 1980, 1989). Thus, based on these concepts, ethics or morality is an individual moral guide on how one should make decisions against self-interest. Those who are living in a society or community must subscribe to such moral principles. These moral principles or moral rules should be integrated into one’s behavior/actions and referred to as personal ethics (Jacorzynski, n.d).

Personal ethics in this sense is not just about situational ethics or contextual ethics which is opposed to universal ethics. It is not just an ethical system that focuses on the role of agents and their moral dispositions, in opposition to any ethics centered on impersonal values, God, rules, principles, and rights. Personal ethics is more about a doctrine

that has been chosen as a moral guide in the life of an agent (Jacorzynski (n.d). In this sense, it is an individual commitment to be guided by moral doctrines. As Jacorzynski (n.d) pointed out that to be committed morally, one must subscribe to certain values and put them into practice. In this sense, morality is not a choice, but it is a categorical imperative, a command for all moral agents regardless of their desires or extenuating circumstances. Therefore, they are abiding by everyone (Johnson & Cureton, 2022).

The Philosophy of Work

Merriam – Webster (n.d) defines work as “exerting oneself physically or mentally, especially in sustained effort for a purpose or under compulsion or necessity”. This definition suggests that work is not limited to physical effort but is also a mental effort for a certain objective or purpose. Under this definition, the purpose is not exclusive. A similar definition is also found in Online Dictionary which defines work as “activity involving mental or physical effort done to achieve a purpose or result”. This definition is also not exclusive because it does not indicate specifically the purpose. The two definitions do not identify the result or the purpose of work which suggests not only for monetary profit as capitalism, or totalitarianism, where its purpose is for the good of the community or state (Little, 1948) and not for self-interest. These two concepts (Capitalism and Totalitarianism) have been considered wrong notions of work. According to the totalitarians, the existence of a person is measured in terms of contribution to the community or state. This concept fits perfectly when a group of people or society demand sacrifices from the workers making slaves to the community or organization. Communism reinforces this concept by emphasizing the idea that manual labor is worthy of the name of work (Little, 1948). If totalitarianism overemphasizes the worker as a slave for the community or state, capitalism undervalues the importance of the worker. For capitalism, the only purpose of work is money for a living. The worker then is a wage slave because it is the only way to obtain a means of life.

In resolving these concepts of work, little, (1948) defines work in two senses. In a narrow sense, work is manual labor and in a broader sense, work is a deliberate production by man to change matter for man. Manual labor or any kind of actual operation is directly a change of matter. By working, one generates goods, be it material objects, experiences, or a state of mind (Cholbi, 2022) that others can value and enjoy. Thus, in many cases, a person or a worker is compensated because their labor contributes to the production of goods that have objective value (Cholbi, 2022). The concept suggests that work is not limited to physical work, but also the mental effort that directs those who change matter or who produce goods that are valued by others.

Concerning the purpose of work, Little (1948) pointed out that it is not only for the good of the community or state and not only for obtaining wages for a living but work is for the perfection of the self because, by nature, man is intended to be a worker as part of his natural purpose (Little, 1948) and therefore life without work is against human nature and a man by his/her nature is a worker and is his/her purpose and through work, man perfects his nature by doing some of the visible good in the material world. These concepts emphasize the point that work is a central-life interest (Sharma and Rai, 2015). Thus, work is good in itself to the worker since it is his/her purpose to perfect himself/herself and not for the good of others or money and thus, he/she should be content with his/her achievement by doing a good job, even if he/she is not rewarded or praised because work is own reward.

The philosophy of work (Little, 1948) is against its contemporary concept related to employment. Work is seen as an instrument to make money because the workers sell their labor in exchange for wages. Following the concept of work provided by Little (1948), this should not always be associated with employment to gain money for a living (Cholbi, 2022). Many people work without being paid since they work for themselves and not for others. Thus, the value of work does not depend on the exchange value of performing work otherwise; work becomes a burden (Cholbi, 2022). In this case, no intrinsic value of the work exists. Aristotle as cited in Clark (2017) emphasized that work is an exercise of human rationality, in the sense that human perfects him/her through work. Work, therefore, is the realization of humans as rational beings, because t, through work, they develop and exercise their rational power ((Elster 1989, Sayers 2005).

The Concept of Work Ethics

Based on the philosophy of work, it is seen as physical and mental efforts for self-perfection. Further, work is an integral part of man because work is the nature of man. By nature, man is intended to be a worker as part of his/her natural purpose (Little, 1948). Work should not be associated with employment and a means of making a living because it is the life of man. Emanating from the basic philosophical view of work, work ethics have been defined differently by different researchers with different emphases.

Bazzy (2018) views work ethics as “an individual’s attitude toward work and effortful activities”. This definition does not indicate what the attitudes toward work are and what the purpose of effortful activities is. This confusion can be explained by Bouma, (1973), and Nelson, (1973) as they define work ethics as “a belief in the value and importance of work for its own sake”. Based on this definition, the purpose of work is for its own sake and not for any other things because work is an essential part of human existence. This definition is consistent with the philosophy of work that work is natural and part of human nature. While Lessnoff (1994) considers work ethic as “a complete and relentless devotion to one’s economic role on earth”. His definition shows that work is a fulfillment of the “homo economicus” (economic man) nature of human beings (Petrovic, 2008). Homo economicus theory suggests that man is a rational being who decides and pursues wealth for self-interest (Efeoğlu & Çalışkan, 2018). In other words, economic production is the determining factor of man or society (Petrovic, 2008). This concept may not be necessarily in contradiction with the philosophy of work as a part of human nature and a means for self-perfection because the purpose of rational power is to change matter into goods that have objective value (Cholbi, 2022). This concept explains that man is a creative being and able to realize his/their nature as a rational being through his/her creativity, activity, or work (Petrovic, 2008).

Related to the effect of work ethics on outcomes, many studies have been conducted. Bazzy (2015) pointed out that work ethic particularly hard work is associated with success. This was already pointed out by an earlier study by Mudrack (1997) which concluded that individuals who are holding strong work ethics tend to be more committed, satisfied, and engaged in their job. This result is like the research finding of Marri, et al (2012) which measures the effect of work ethics on organizational commitment and turnover intention. The study found that work ethics are significantly correlated with organizational commitment and turnover intention. The same result is also found in the studies of Ud Din, et al (2019), Athar, et al (2016), Udin, et al (2022), Aflah, et al. (2021), and bin Salahudin, et al.

(2016) which work ethic affects job performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment.

There have been conflicts among researchers concerning the measurement of work ethics. Miller (2002) asserted that work ethics is a multidimensional construct composed of several dimensions namely work-related activity, attitudes and beliefs, and motivation which is reflected in behavior. According to him, work ethics does not refer to a particular job and behavior and does not reflect any religious beliefs and values because it is purely secular. Bazy (2018) also considers work ethics to be a multidimensional construct that is consisted of two dimensions which are hard work and self-reliance. Van Ness, et al. (2010) further view work ethics as a multidimensional construct that includes seven dimensions: self-reliance, morality/ethics, leisure, hard work, the centrality of work, waste of time, and delay of gratification. However, Sharma and Rai (2015) rejected the multidimensional measures of work ethics on the basis that these dimensions were not going through a rigorous assessment of the validity. These were based on the protestant work ethics construct which is against the philosophy of work ethics to be secular and free of religious belief. They constructed their scale to measure work ethics and their study concluded moral attitude toward work and the motivation for work. Sharma and Rai (2015) successfully found that work ethic is a single-dimensional construct. This is composed of three components namely work centrality, moral approach to work, and intrinsic work motivation. According to them, these are treated under the work ethics dimension which contains the attitude toward work, the construct, the 10-item work ethics scale, and passed through convergent and discriminant validity.

In the current study, the single-dimensional construct of Sharma and Rai (2015) was adopted because this is in line with the philosophy of work and zeroed in on the attitude toward work. Moreover, the 10-item work ethics scale of Sharma and Rai (2015) was because it is free from religious biases and has been tested.

The Concept of Work Performance and Its Dimensions

The success of an organization will always depend on the management and employees. Management has to assign duties and responsibilities to each member of the organization according to their capabilities and define strategies on how to guide work processes and how to motivate employees so that they are motivated to perform their tasks. Given those requirements in place, however, it is not a guarantee that individual employees will successfully perform their tasks and achieve their objectives. Individual employees' performance is always caused by other different factors in the organization. Besides leadership and management, performance is also caused by many different other factors like job satisfaction (Inuwa, 2016, Ouedraogo & Leclerc, 2013, Christen, et al, 2006), engagement (Motyka, 2018), commitment (Rebeka, 2019), work environment (Saidi, et al, 2019), skills and other personal factors like self-efficacy (Abun, et al, 2021), and entrepreneurial mindset (Abun, et al, 2021). Monitoring these factors may help the management to improve employees' performance. This is crucially important because once the performance is affected negatively by these dimensions, the organizational objectives can suffer. Kim and Ployhart (2014) as cited by Abun, et al (2022) pointed out that individual work performance is the building block on which the entire economy is based. The same case with the organization, it is individual work performance that can bring the organization to reach its vision and mission.

Knowing the crucial importance of work performance, there have been efforts to define and measure it. Motowidlo

(2003, Motowidlo & Kell, 2012) defined job performance as “the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioral episodes that an individual carries out over a specified period”. This definition emphasizes two key issues. First, performance is an aggregated property of multiple, discrete behavior that occur over time. Second, the property of behavior to which it refers to its expected value to the organization (Martocchio, 2015). This concept suggests that it is the expected organizational value of what people do, and it does not refer to tangible outputs or results. It is about the behavior that contributes something of value to the organization. Performance does not include the outcome or results of individual employees’ behavior. This is often the control of the employees. Patro (2017) defines work performance as “an accomplishment of the assigned tasks for achieving an organization’s goal”. This definition measures it from the output perspective. Campbell (1990) defines work performance as a means to reach a goal or set of goals within a job, role, or organization, but not the actual consequences of the acts performed within a job. Campbell (1990) confirms that performance is not a single action but a complex activity. It is strictly behavior and separated from the outcome.

Motowidlo (2003), Motowidlo & Kell, 2012), and Campbell (1990) defined job performance as focusing on the behavior that contributes to or detracts from the value of the organization and the expected organizational value of the behavior. The definition of Motowidlo and Kell (2012), shows that there is one single concern to measure: individual behavior (Motowidlo (2003). The result depends on other factors such as leadership and situational constraints beyond the control of the employees. This point is affirmed by Campbell (1990) that performance is strictly behavior and not the outcome. Thus, it is directed toward the sets of behavior that affect organizational effectiveness.

Most researchers settled on the common agreement that works performance is a multidimensional construct (Kaplan & Norton, (1992); Moore, (1995). Kaplan and Norton, (1992); Moore, (1995); and Nalwoga, (2016) identified four dimensions namely inputs where the focus is on the resources used to produce the product and services, an activity that is focused on the action taken to produce the product/services, the output which focuses on the volume of products and services produced and outcome focused on the impact of products and services produced. Looking at these different dimensions, Kaplan & Norton, (1992); Moore, (1995) view work performance from two aspects which are the output and the behavior which is contradicted by Motowidlo (2003), and Motowidlo and Kell (2012) in which they focused on the behavior only. While Draghici, et al. (2014) hold that measuring performance can be from three sources namely efficiency, effectiveness, and pertinence. On one hand, efficiency refers to the level of performance that uses the lowest number of inputs to produce the greater amount of outputs. On the other hand, effectiveness relates to the use of all inputs to produce any given output including personal time and energy which lead to the attainment of organizational objectives. While pertinence measures the organizational leader/manager's behavior. Draghici (2014) seems to define performance from the output perspective but is interesting to note that efficiency and effectiveness are the product of work behavior. While Motowidlo (2003), Motowidlo and Kell (2012), identified three dimensions of work performance which are task behavior, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior. Campbell (2012) includes technical performance (the belief that all work role requires technical performance), communication (proficiency with which one conveys information that is clear, understandable, compelling, and well organized), Initiative, persistence, and effort (refers to conscientious initiative), counterproductive work behavior (behaviors that harm the organization), supervisory, managerial, executive (refers to leadership performance in a

hierarchical relationship), hierarchical management performance (actions that deal with generating, preserving, and allocating the organization's resources to best achieve its goals), peer/team member leadership performance(actions that are in the context of peer or team member interrelationships), and peer/team member management performance (actions related to planning, organizing, problem-solving).

Campbell and Wiernik (2015) later found that many variables presented in different studies do not measure individual work performance because different researchers have different definitions and conceptual frameworks. To solve such a problem, Campbell and Wiernik (2015) suggest developing a consensus on the definition of individual work performance. As a result of their suggestion, a consensus on the definition of work performance is established. All agree that individual job performance is what people do, and the actions they take that contribute to the organization's goals (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015).

Following such an agreement, the concern of individual work performance evaluation is the actions taken by the employees that contribute to the attainment of organizational goals whether they are written or not written in the job description. The agreement is that work performance has nothing to do with the other determining factors of performance such as knowledge, skills, and choice of behavior. Though these factors affect performance, however, they are not the performance itself. Motowidlo et al. (1997) held that performance is related to actions or behavior that directly affects the attainment of organizational goals and it is not about the outcome of performance or efficiency or productivity (Campbell, 2013 b). Based on those many elements of individual work performance, Koopmans, et.al (2011) simplify and identified three major dimensions of work performance which include task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior. These three dimensions encompass the content of different dimensions identified by Campbell (2012), Motowidlo (1997), Motowidlo (2003), Motowidlo and Kell, (2012) and Organ (1988).

Task performance as defined by Borman & Motowidlo, (1993) and cited by Silong, et al. (2013) is “the effectiveness with which job incumbents carry out activities that contribute to the organization's "technical core" either directly by executing a part of its technical process or indirectly by providing it with needed materials or services”. This definition refers to competency and expertise one has in performing his/her functions effectively (Harrison, Newman, & Roth, 2006) which is called by Campbell (1990) task proficiency or technical core. These are the behaviors that directly affect the completion of the task and contribute to the technical core of the organization. This is the basic requirement when one is given a certain task, that he/she should possess the basic knowledge and skills to perform the task at hand.

Contextual performance is defined by Dođru (2019) as “the degree to which an employee behaves positively consisting of volunteering for extra duties, helping coworkers, and cooperating with them with an expectation of a reward”. Organ (1988) considered these behaviors as organizational citizenship behavior. These are exercised voluntarily beyond the job description. These maintain and enhance the organizational environment and help employees perform. Though these behaviors are not required by the organization, they are important to help employees perform their main tasks. Studies have shown that contextual performance relates to task performance (Diaz-Vilela, et al. 2015), and effectiveness (Griffin, et.al., 2001).

Counterproductive work behavior is defined as negative behaviors that harm the organization and other people who are working in that organization (Spector & Fox, 2005). These are directed toward the organization and the individuals within the organization (Robinson & Bennett, 1995). This included abuse production deviance, sabotage, theft, and withdrawal (Spector, et al. 2006 as cited by Ispas & Borman, 2015). Concerning the workgroup, counterproductive work behavior (CWB) may include laissez-faire in which a person or leader of a group does not care to supervise the work, violating group norms or policy, destroying the working relationships and applying one's values (Braun & Hentschel, 2015). The main objective of CWB is intended to fail the organization to achieve its objectives. It captures a wide range of behaviors that are consciously done to undermine organizational performance with hidden motivations.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Sharma and Rai (2015) Koopmans, et al. (2011), and Abun, et al. (2022)

Figure 1: The conceptual framework explains the concept of the study. It shows that work ethics affects individual work performance along three sub-variables namely task, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior.

Statement of the Problems

The study determined the effect of work ethics on individual work performance along with tasks, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior. It answered the following questions:

1. **What is the work ethics of employees in terms of:**
 - 1.1 the work itself;
 - 1.2 moral attitude; and
 - 1.3 intrinsic motivation?
2. **What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:**
 - 2.1 task performance;
 - 2.2 contextual performance; and
 - 2.3 counterproductive behavior?
3. **Is there a relationship between work ethics and individual work performance?**

Assumptions

The study assumed that work ethics affects the behavior of employees in carrying out their duties and responsibilities and they can be measured.

Hypothesis

The study of Bazy (2015) and Mudrack (1997) found that work ethics are correlated to success and those who have higher work ethics tend to be more committed, satisfied, and engaged in their work than those who have lower work ethics. Based on these findings, the current study hypothesized that the work ethics of employees affect their work performance.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the study is the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag and delimits its investigation along with the effect of work ethics on individual work performance in terms of task, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

Research Methodology

As demanded by scientific inquiry, research must follow a certain methodology of investigation. The methodology explains the process, particularly how the study identifies, selects, processes, and analyses information about a topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). The study followed the rule of procedures in the investigation by determining the research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the Study

The study applied a descriptive assessment, and correlational research design to determine the level of corporate governance practices and individual work performance. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study were all employees of the Divine Word Colleges of Laoag in Ilocos Norte. A total of 170 employees were taken as the sample of the study. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used.

Data Gathering Instruments

The data were gathered through research questionnaires. The study adopted the instruments of Sharma and Rai (2015) on work ethics and concerning individual work performance, the questionnaires were taken from Koopmans, et al. (2011) and adopted by Abun, et.al. (2022).

Data Gathering Procedures

The integrity and quality of research did not only depend on the content but also on the process of the study. Before the researcher distributed the questionnaires, a letter was sent to the president of the college to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in his respective institution. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requested employee representatives to retrieve the data from the respondents.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the procedures and content of the paper which neither violated ethical standards nor caused harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of work ethics and individual work performance and the ANOVA (analysis of variance) was used to measure the correlation between work ethics and individual performance of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents data that was gathered through research questionnaires and the presentation follows the statement of the problems. The data are in the table and followed by the analysis.

Problem 1: What is the work ethics of employees in terms of:

- 1.1. the work itself;
- 1.2. moral attitude;
- 1.3. intrinsic motivation?

Table 1: Work Ethics of Employees (n=165)

Work Ethics	Mean	Description
A. Work Itself		
1. I consider my occupational career to be one of the most important activities in my life	4.1	A
2. I believe that a person is known in society by the work he does	4.1	A
3. I believe that a person is known in society by the work he does	4.0	A
4. Even if I don't have to work to earn a living, I would still prefer to continue working	4.0	A
5. I believe that work provides a powerful channel to express one's knowledge, ability, and creativity.	4.0	A

Composite Mean	4.04	A
B. Moral Attitude toward Work		
1. Even in this fast-changing world, sincerity, hard work, and integrity continue to be the golden keys to success in one's work life.	4.0	A
1. I feel a moral obligation to give a full day's work for a full day's pay.	4.0	A
3. I believe that one should never be last for work unless there is some real emergency	4.0	A
Composite Mean	4.0	A
C. Intrinsic Motivation		
1. I believe that a job well done is a reward in itself	4.0	A
2. I welcome jobs that involve greater responsibility and challenge as they contribute to my learning and growth	4.0	A
Composite Mean	4.0	A
Overall Mean	4.01	A

Source: Sharma and Rai (2015).

Legend:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Based on the data presented in the table, shows that the work ethics of employees obtained a composite mean of 4.01 which is considered "agree or high". Even when the dimensions of work ethics are taken singly, all the three dimensions such as the attitude toward the work itself, moral attitude toward the work, and intrinsic motivation are evaluated within the same level of composite mean rating with the interpretation of "agree or high". This means that to a high degree, they believe that their occupational career is one of the most important activities in their life, a person is known in society by the work he does, even if they don't have to work to earn a living, they would still prefer to continue working, and work provides a powerful channel to express one's knowledge, ability and creativity. From their moral attitude toward work, they also agree that sincerity, hard work, and integrity continue to be the golden keys to success in one's work life. In terms of their intrinsic motivation, the employees believe that a job well done is a reward and they also welcome a job that involves greater responsibility and challenge as they contribute to my learning and growth.

2. What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:

- 2.1 task performance;
- 2.2 contextual performance;
- 2.3 counterproductive behavior?

Table 2. Individual work performance of employees in terms of Task performance (n=165)

Task Performance	Mean	Description
1. I manage to plan my work so that it was done on time	4.00	A/H

2. My planning was optimal	4.10	A/H
3. I kept in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work	4.10	A/H
4. I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work	4.10	A/H
5. I knew how to set the right priorities	4.00	A/H
6. I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort	4.10	A/H
Composite Mean	4.06	A/H

Source: Koopmans, et al., (2011) and Abun, et al., (2022).

The data in the table reveals that the individual work performance of employees in terms of task performance gained a composite mean of 4.06 which is interpreted as “agree or high”. Even if the task performance items are taken singly, all the items are evaluated within the same range of mean rating with the same interpretation of “agree or high”. It suggests that to a high degree, the employees manage to plan their work so that it was done on time, keep in mind the results that they must achieve in their work, separate main issues from side issues at work, know how to set the right priorities and the ability to perform my work well with minimal time and effort. Although knowledge and skills are not the only main factors in predicting work performance, they are still considered to be the most important contributors to job performance as acknowledged by many researchers (Imam, et al., 2018, Eylon & Reif, 1984, Naumann, 2019, Sanderson, 1989).

Table 3: Work Performance in terms of Contextual Performance (n=165)

Contextual Performance	Mean	Description
1. I took on extra responsibilities	4.00	A/H
2. I started a new task myself when my old ones were finished	4.00	A/H
3. I took on a challenging work task, when available	4.00	A/H
4. I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date	4.00	A/H
5. I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date	4.00	A/H
6. I came up with creative solutions to new problems	4.00	A
7. I kept looking for new challenges in my job	4.00	A/H
8. I did more than was expected of me	4.00	A/H
9. I actively participated in work meetings	4.00	A/H
10. I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work	4.00	A/H
11. I grasped opportunities when they presented themselves	4.00	A/H
12. I knew how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly	4.00	A/H
Composite Mean	4.00	A/H

Source: Koopmans, et al., (2011) and Abun, et al., (2022).

The data on the table demonstrates that the individual work performance of employees in terms of contextual performance received is 4.00 which is interpreted as "agree or high". Even if the items are taken separately, all items are rated within the same range of mean level with the interpretation of "agree or high" such as taking extra responsibilities, starting a new task themselves when the old ones were finished, taking on a challenging work task, when available, keeping their job knowledge and skills up-to-date, coming up with creative solutions to new problems, looking for new challenges in their job, doing more than was expected of them, actively participating in work meetings, actively looking for ways to improve their performance at work, grasping opportunities when they presented themselves, and knowing how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly. Contextual performance plays an important contribution to organizational performance and thus the management needs to manage those behaviors that are helping the organization by rewarding the positive behavior of employees (Reily & Aronson, 2012).

Table 4: Individual Work Performance along with Counterproductive Behavior (n=165).

Counterproductive Behavior	Mean	Description
1. I complained about unimportant matters at work	2.00	D/L
2. I made problems greater than they were at work	2.00	D/L
3. I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	2.20	D/L
4. I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work	2.00	D/L
5. I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work	2.00	D/L
6. I did less than was expected of me	2.00	D/L
7. I managed to get off from a work task easily	2.00	D/L
8. I sometimes did nothing, when I should have been working	2.20	D/L
Composite Mean	2.05	D/L

Source: Koopmans, et al., (2011) and Abun, et al., (2022).\

Legend:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

As indicated, the data displays that the individual work performance of employees concerning counterproductive behavior gained a composite mean rating of 2.05 which is referring to "disagree or low". This rating implies that employees of the institution have low counterproductive behavior. Even if the items are taken separately, all items have the same mean rating with the interpretation of “disagree or low” such as complaining about unimportant matters at work, making problems greater than they were at work, focusing on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects, speaking with colleagues about the negative aspects of their work, speaking with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of their work, doing less than was expected of them, and doing nothing, while they should have been working. It is important to keep these counterproductive behaviors low because they can affect the organization as stated by Sypniewska (2020), it might result in financial, personal, and organizational costs.

Problem 3. Is there a relationship between work ethics and individual work performance?

Table 5: Work Ethics & Task Performance

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.832 ^a	.692	.686	.31214

a. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	35.183	3	11.728	120.372	.000 ^b
Residual	15.686	161	.097		
Total	50.870	164			

a. Dependent Variable: Task performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.728	.185		3.939	.000
Work itself	.267	.091	.267	2.950	.004
Moral attitude	.113	.080	.118	1.408	.161
Intrinsic motivation	.447	.072	.495	6.206	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Task performance

The employees' work ethics in terms of work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation taken together significantly predicted the task performance of the employees, $F(3,164) = 120.372$, $p < .01$ with .832 overlap between the three predictor variables.

Particularly, intrinsic motivation $B = .447$, $p < .01$ and work itself $B = .267$, $p < .01$, .728 quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

Hence, the employees' work ethics in terms of work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation, when taken together, could predict the employees' task performance.

However, when the factors of work ethics were taken separately, it was only intrinsic motivation and work itself that could predict the employees' task performance.

Table 6: Work Ethics & Contextual Performance Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.792 ^a	.627	.620	.32226

a. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	28.111	3	9.370	90.228	.000 ^b
Residual	16.720	161	.104		
Total	44.831	164			

a. Dependent Variable: Contextual performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized	t	Sig.
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			Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.965	.191		5.053	.000
1 Work itself	.381	.094	.405	4.067	.000
Moral attitude	.033	.083	.037	.398	.691
Intrinsic motivation	.333	.074	.393	4.473	.000

The DWCL employees’ work ethics as to work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation as a group significantly predicted their contextual performance, $F(3,164) = 90.228$, $p < .01$ with .792 overlap between the three factors of work ethics.

Specifically, work itself $B = .381$, $p < .01$ and intrinsic motivation $B = .333$, $p < .01$, .965 quantified the Y-intercept of the regression equation.

Thus, the DWCL employees’ work ethics in terms of work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation when taken together could predict their contextual performance.

However, when the work ethics factors were taken separately, it is only worked itself and intrinsic motivation which could predict the employees' contextual performance.

Table 7: Work Ethics & Counterproductive Behavior

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.442 ^a	.195	.180	.79241

a. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	24.505	3	8.168	13.009	.000 ^b
Residual	101.093	161	.628		
Total	125.598	164			

a. Dependent Variable: Counterproductive behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.941	.469		10.526	.000
1 Work itself	.148	.230	.094	.643	.521
Moral attitude	-.478	.203	-.320	-2.357	.020
Intrinsic motivation	-.329	.183	-.231	-1.795	.074

a. Dependent Variable: Counterproductive behavior

The work ethics of the DWCL employees as to work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation taken together, significantly predicted their counterproductive behavior, $F(3,164) = 13.009$, $p < .01$ with .442 overlap

between the three predictor variables.

Particularly, moral attitude $B = -.478$, $p < .05$, 4.941 quantified the Y-intercept of the regression equation. Hence, the employees' work ethics in terms of work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation when taken together could predict their counterproductive behavior.

However, when the work ethics factors were taken separately, it was only a moral attitude that could predict the employees' counterproductive behavior.

Table 8: Work Ethics & Overall Performance

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.529 ^a	.280	.267	.28796

a. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.190	3	1.730	20.863	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.351	161	.083		
	Total	18.541	164			

a. Dependent Variable: Overall performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intrinsic motivation, Moral attitude, Work itself

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.209	.171		12.953	.000
	Work itself	.266	.084	.440	3.176	.002
	Moral attitude	-.111	.074	-.193	-1.505	.134
	Intrinsic motivation	.151	.067	.277	2.269	.025

a. Dependent Variable: Overall performance

The work ethics of employees such as work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation, when taken as a group, significantly predicted the employees' overall work performance, $F(3,164) = 20.863$, $p < .01$ with .529 overlap between the three factors.

Specifically, work itself $B = .266$, $p < .01$ and intrinsic motivation $B = .151$, $p < .05$, 2.209 quantified the Y-intercept of the regression equation.

Thus, the employees' work ethics in terms of work itself, moral attitude, and intrinsic motivation, when taken together, could predict their overall performance.

However, when the factors of work ethics were taken singly, it only worked itself and intrinsic motivation which could predict the overall performance of the employees.

Results and Discussion

Analyzing the result of the current study leads to an in-depth discussion on the influence of the work ethics of

employees on their work performance. The finding of the study denotes that management needs to pay attention to the work ethics of the employees because it significantly affects their work performance. Special attention must be given to the three dimensions, particularly the attitude of employees toward the work, their moral attitude toward the work, and their intrinsic motivation. To improve task performance and contextual performance, the management may look into the attitude of employees toward their work, specifically how they view their work with their life and their intrinsic motivation. In terms of the effect of attitude-related factors on work performance, Abun, et al., (2021) and Cabrera and Estacio (2022) have found a correlation between the two variables. These findings support the current proposition that management needs to enhance the attitude of employees toward their work performance. As Ajzen (1993) argued that attitude affects work behavior. It should also be noted that the study of Bazigos and Caruzo (2016) indicated that employees who are intrinsically motivated are more committed, satisfied, and perform better.

The current study also pointed out further that it is not only attitude and work motivation that matter to the employees, but it is also their moral point of view toward work. Their moral point of view can affect their work performance, particularly counterproductive behavior. In other words, the more ethical the employees are, the lesser they practice counterproductive behavior. This suggests that the management needs to strengthen the moral values of the employees, particularly those that affect their work behavior as recommended by Cohen et. at. (2014). Employees who have a high level of moral values tend to consider the needs and interests of others which consequently affects their work performance. The management would want to explore providing employees with training and development knowledge, skills, proper motivation, and ethical behavior. One must consider that knowledge and skills alone without proper motivation and a moral attitude toward work will not improve work performance.

Conclusion

The study determined the effect of the work ethics of employees on individual work performance. The work ethics of employees along three components (the attitude toward work itself, moral attitude toward work, and intrinsic motivation) are considered high and their work performance along with task and contextual performance are also considered high, except the counterproductive behavior which is low. In terms of the relationship between work ethics and individual work performance, the result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) concludes that overall, there is a significant correlation between work ethics and individual work performance. However, when taken singly, the study found that attitude toward the work itself and intrinsic motivation affect the individual work performance, while moral attitude toward work does not affect the task and contextual performance but affects counterproductive behavior.

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References

- Abun, D., Basilio, G.J.Q., Fredolin, J.P., & Magallanes, T. (2021). The effect of the entrepreneurial mindset, and work environment on employees' work performance. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v11i4.1839>
- Abun, D., Nicolas, M.T., & Apollo, E.P. (2021). Employees' self-efficacy and work performance of employees as mediated by the work environment. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(7),01-15. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i7.1470>
- Abun, D., Ranay, F.B., Magallanes, T., & Encarnacion, M.J. (2022). The effect of corporate governance on the individual work performance of employees: The case of private higher education. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), Center for the Strategic Studies in Business and Finance, vol. 11(3), 92-98. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v11i3.1763>
- Abun, D., Ubaso, A.L.A., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Ranay, F.B. (2021). Attitude toward the work and its influence on the Individual work performance of employees: Basis for Attitude Management. *Technium: Social Science Journal*, 18, 378-394.
- Acton, H.B. (1970). *Kant's Moral Philosophy*. Macmillan: St. Martin's Press, 24-25.
- Aflah, K. N., Suharnomo, S., Mas'ud, F., & Mursid, A. (2021). Islamic Work Ethics and Employee Performance: The Role of Islamic Motivation, Affective Commitment, and Job Satisfaction. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(1), 997–1007. <https://doi.org/10.13106/JAFEB.2021.VOL8.NO1.997>
- Ajzen, I. (1993). *Attitude Theory and Attitude-Behavior Relation*. New York: Walter de Gruyter.
- Ariola, M.M. (2006). *Principles and Methods of Research*. Manila: Rex Book Store
- Articulo, A.C. (2004). *Moral Philosophy*. Manila: Great Books Publishing.
- Athar, M.R., Shahzad, K., Amad, J. & Ijaz, M.S. (2016). Impact of Islamic Work Ethics on Organizational Commitment: Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Islamic Business and Management*, 6(1).
- Banister, C. (2017). *Work Ethic, Turnover, and Performance: An Examination of Predictive Validity for Entry-level Employees*. Dissertations. 705. Retrieved from <https://irl.umsl.edu/dissertation/705>
- Bataineh, M. T. (2020). The Effect of Work Ethics on Job Performance in International SMEs in Al-Hassan Industrial Estate. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2020, 10(5), 154-158. <https://doi.org/10.32479/irmm.10364>
- Bazigos, M. & Caruzo, E. (2016). Why Frontline Workers are Disengaged. *McKinsey Quarterly*. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/>
- Bazzy, J.D. (2018). Work Ethic Dimensions as Predictors of Ego Depletion. *Curr Psychol* 37, 198–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-016-9503-6>
- bin Salahudin, S.N., binti Baharudin, S.S., Abdullah, M.S. & Osman, A. (2016). The Effect of Islamic Work Ethics

- on Organizational Commitment. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35, 582-590. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00071-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00071-X)
- bin Salahudina, S.N., bin Alwia, N.R., binti Baharuddin, S.S., & binti Halimata, S.S. (2016). The Relationship between Work Ethics and Job Performance. 3rd International Conference on Business and Economics, 21 - 23 September 2016. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/RSEARCH-PC1/Downloads/The_Relationship_between_Work_Ethics_and_Job_Perfo.pdf
- Borman, W. C., & Motowidlo, S. J. (1993). Expanding the criterion domain to include elements of contextual performance. *Personnel selection in organizations*, 71-98. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Bouma, G.D. (1973). Beyond Lenski: A critical review of recent 'Protestant ethic' research. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 12(2), 141–155.
- Braun, S. & Hentschel, T. (2015). Group Process in Organization. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (Second Edition). Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Cabrera, W. & Estacio, D. (2022). Job Attitude as a Factor on Job Performance. *International Journal of Economics Development Research*, 3(1), 13-35. <https://doi.org/10.37385/ijedr.v3i1.254>
- Campbell, J. (1990). Modelling the performance prediction problem in industrial and organizational psychology. In M. Dunnette & L. Hough (Eds.). *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 686–707). Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press
- Campbell, J.P. I(2013b). Leadership, the old, the new, and the timeless: a commentary. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195398793.013.0024>
- Campbell, J.P. & Wiernik, B.M. (2015). The Modeling and Assessment of Work Performance. *The Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 2, 47-74. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032414-111427>
- Campbell, J. P. (2012). Behaviour, performance, and effectiveness in the twenty-first century. In S. W. J. Kozlowski (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of organizational psychology*, 1 (1), 159–194). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199928309.013.0006>
- Cholbi, M. (2022). Philosophical Approaches to Work and Labor. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2022/entries/work-labor/>.
- Christen, M., Iyer, G. & Soberman, D. (2006). Job Satisfaction, Job Performance, and Effort: A Reexamination Using Agency Theory. *Journal of Marketing*, 70, 137-150. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.2006.70.1.137>
- Clark, S. (2017). Good Work. *Journal of Applied Philosophy*, 34: 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/japp.12137>
- Cohen, T. R., Panter, A. T., Turan, N., Morse, L. A., & Kim, Y. (2014). Moral character in the workplace. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0037245>.
- Cornel Law School (1992). Ethics. Legal Information Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/ethics>

- Diaz-Vilela, L.F. Rodriquez, N.D., Isla-Diaz, R., Diaz-Cebrera, D., Hernandez-Fernaud, E., & Rosales-Sacnchez, C. (2015). Relationships between Contextual and Task Performance and Interrater Agreement: Are There Any? *Plos One*, 10(10), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139898>
- Doğru, C. (2019). The Effects of Perceived Organizational Support and Leader-Member Exchange on Contextual Performance: A Study in the Banking Sector. In *Handbook of Research on Contemporary Approaches in Management and Organizational Strategy Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge*.
- Draghici, A., Popescu, A.D., & Gogan, L.M. (2014). A proposed model for monitoring organizational performance. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 124, 544 – 551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.02.518>
- Efeoğlu, I.E. & Çalışkan, Y. (2018). A Brief History of Homo Economicus From the Economics Discipline Perspective. *Adana Alparslan Türkeş Science and Technology University Journal of Social Science*, 2(1), 28-36.
- Eylon, B.-S., & Reif, F. (1984). Effects of Knowledge Organization on Task Performance. *Cognition and Instruction*, 1(1), 5–44. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3233519>.
- Elster, J. (1989). Self-realisation in Work and Politics. In J. Elster and K.O. Moene (eds.), *Alternatives to Capitalism*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 127–158. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0265052500000327>
- Gert, B. & Gert, J. (2020). The Definition of Morality. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/morality-definition/>.
- Grannan, C. (n.d). What's the Difference Between Morality and Ethics? *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/story/whats-the-difference-between-morality-and-ethics>
- Griffin, M., Neal, A. & Neale, M. (2001). The Contribution of Task Performance and Contextual Performance to Effectiveness: Investigating the Role of Situational Constraints. *Applied Psychology*, 49(3), 517-533. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1464-0597.00029>
- Harrison, D. A., Newman, D. A., & Roth, P. L. (2006). How Important Are Job Attitudes? Meta-Analytic Comparisons of Integrative Behavioral Outcomes and Time Sequences. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(2), 305-325. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2006.20786077>
- Helen R. Benedicto & Merlita V. Caelian (2021). The Influence of Work Ethics on Job Performance of Government Employees. *Philippines Social Science Journal*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i1.313>
- Imam, O.A., Abas-Mastura, M. & Osman, S. (2018). Employability Skills and Task Performance of Employees in Government Sector. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(4), 150-162
- Inuwa, M. (2016). Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance: An Empirical Approach. *The Millennium University Journal*, 1(1), 90-103.
- Ispas, D. & Borman, W.C. (2015). *Counterproductive Work Behavior*. Amsterdam: Elsevier
- Jacorzynski, W. (n.d). Personal Ethics. Retrieved from <https://www.eolss.net/sample-chapters/C14/E1-37-02-01.pdf>
- Johnson, R. & Cureton, A. (2022). Kant's Moral Philosophy. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2022/entries/kant-moral/>.

- Kaplan, R.S. and Norton, D.P. (1992). Putting the balanced scorecard measures that drive performance. *Harvard Business Review*, 70(1), 71–79.
- Kim, Y & Ployhart, R. E. (2014). The effects of staffing and training on firm productivity and profit growth before, during, and after the Great Recession. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 99, 361–89. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035408>
- Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C.M., Hildebrandt, V.H., Schaufeli, W.B., de Vet, H.C.W., & van der Beek, A.J. (2011). Conceptual Frameworks of Individual Work Performance A Systematic Review. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 53 (8). <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0b013e318226a763>
- Leedy, P.D. (1974). *Practical Research: Planning and Design*. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co., Inc
- Lessnoff, M.H. (1994). *The spirit of capitalism and the Protestant ethic: An enquiry into the Weber thesis*. Brookfield, VT: E. Elgar.
- Little, A. (1948). The Philosophy of Work. *The Irish Monthly*, 76(896), 56–65. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20515765>
- Mack, Mary Peter. *Jeremy Bentham: An Odyssey of Ideas 1748-1792*. London: Heinemann, 1962.
- Marri, M.Y.K., Sadozai, A.M., Zaman, H.M.F., Yousufzai, M.I. & Ramay, M.I. (2012). Measuring Islamic Work Ethics and Its Consequences on Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention: An Empirical Study at Public Sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 2(2).
- Martocchio, J.J. (2015). Pay, Compensation, and Performance. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- McCombes, S. (2020). Descriptive Research. Scribbr. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Work. In the Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved August 28, 2022, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/work>
- Miller, M.J., Woehr, D.J., & Hudspeth, N. (2002). The meaning and measurement of work ethic: Construction and initial validation of a multidimensional inventory. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 60(3), 451–489. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1838>
- Moore, M. (1995). *Creating Public Value: Strategic Management in Government*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press
- Motowidlo, S.J, Borman, W.C., & Schmit M.J. (1997). A theory of individual differences in task and contextual performance. *Human Performance*. 10, 71–83. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327043hup1002_1
- Motowidlo, S. J. (2003). Job performance. In W. C. Borman, D. R. Ilgen, & R. J. Klimoski (Eds.), *Handbook of psychology: Industrial and organizational psychology*, 12, 39–53. New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Motowidlo, S.J. & Kell, H.J. (2012). Job Performance. In book: *Handbook of psychology*, vol. 12: Industrial and organizational psychology. Edition: 2nd. Chapter: Job performance. United Kingdom: Wiley.
- Motyka, B. (2018). Employee engagement and performance: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of*

- Management and Economics 54(3), 227-244. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijme-2018-0018>
- Mudrack, Peter E. (1997). Protestant work-ethic dimensions and work orientations. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 23(2), 217–225.
- Nalwoga, M.M (2016). Organizational performance measurement models, also for poverty alleviation. *International Journal of Water*, 10 (2/3), 122–138. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJW.2016.075564>
- Naumann J (2019). The Skilled, the Knowledgeable, and the Motivated: Investigating the Strategic Allocation of Time on Task in a Computer-Based Assessment. *Frontier in Psychology*. 10, 1429. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01429>
- Nelson, B. (1973). Weber's Protestant ethic: Its origins, wanderings, and foreseeable future. In C. Glock & P. Hammond (Eds), *Beyond the classics* (pp. 71–130). New York: Harper & Row.
- O'Neill, Onora, 1975, *Acting on Principle*, New York: Columbia University Press
- O'Neill, Onora, 1989, *Constructions of Reason*, New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Organ, D.W. (1988). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Good Soldier Syndrome*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books
- Osibanjo, O.A., Akinbode, J.O., Oludayo, O. (2015). Work Ethics and Employees' Job Performance. *Journal of Leadership, Accountability and Ethics* 12(1),107-117.
- Ouedraogo, A. & Leclerc, A. (2013). Job Satisfaction and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Canadian Credit Union. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict* 17(1):35-50
- Painter, R. N.d). *Ethics and Corruption in Business and Government: Interdependence and Adverse Consequences*. The Maurice and Muriel Fulton Lecture Series. The Law School, The University of Chicago. Retrieved from http://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/fulton_lectures
- Patro, C.S. (2017). *Performance Appraisal System Effectiveness: A Conceptual Review*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge.
- Petrovic, G. (2008). Mas as Economic Animal and Mas as Praxis an Interpretation of Marx. *An Interdisciplinary of Philosophy*, 6(1-4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00201746308601366>
- Pojman, L.P. (2000). On the nature and purpose of morality. *The Moral Life*. 32-41. New York, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Rawls, J. (1980). Kantian Constructivism in Moral Theory. *Journal of Philosophy*, 77: 515–72. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2025790>
- Rawls, J. (1989). Themes in Kant's Moral Philosophy. In *Kant's Transcendental Deductions*, E. Förster (ed.), Stanford: Stanford University Press, 81–113.
- Rebeka, K.P.E. (2019). Employee Commitment on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.C4078.098319>

- Reilly, R.R. & Aronson, Z.H. (2012). What is contextual performance? In James W. Smither and Manuel London (Eds), *Performance Management: Putting Research into Practice*. London: Jossey-Bass.
- Robinson, S.L. & Bennett, R.J. (1995). A Typology of Deviant Workplace Behaviors: A Multidimensional Scaling Study. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 38(2):555-572. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256693>
- Saidi, N.S.A., Michael, F.L., Sumilan, H., Lim, S.L.O., & Jonathan, V. (2019). The Relationship Between Working Environment and Employee Performance. *Journal of Cognitive Sciences and Human Development* 5(2):14-22. <https://doi.org/10.33736/jcshd.1916.2019>
- Sanderson, P. M. (1989). Verbalizable knowledge and skilled task performance: Association, dissociation, and mental models. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 15(4), 729–747. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.15.4.729>
- Sen, A. & Williams, B. (eds). (1982). *Utilitarianism and Beyond*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Silong, A.D., Daryoush, Y., Omar, Z., & Othman, J. (2013). Improving Job Performance: Workplace Learning is the First Step. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 1(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.1n.1p.100>
- Singer, P. (2022, August 16). ethics. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/ethics-philosophy>
- Spector, P. E., & Fox, S. (2005). The Stressor-Emotion Model of Counterproductive Work Behavior. In S. Fox & P. E. Spector (Eds.), *Counterproductive work behaviour: Investigations of actors and targets* (pp. 151–174). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10893-007>
- Spector, P. E., Fox, S., Penney, L. M., Bruursema, K., Goh, A., & Kessler, S. (2006). The dimensionality of counterproductivity: Are all counterproductive behaviors created equal? *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68 (3), 446-460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2005.10.005>
- Sunday, M.A. & Michael, K.W. (2018). Work Ethics/Corruption and Organizational Development in Nigeria. *Rainbow Journal*, 1 (1), 151-159.
- Sypniewska, B. (2020). Counterproductive Work Behavior and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Adv Cogn Psychol*. 2020 Dec 10;16(4):321-328. <https://doi.org/10.5709/acp-0306-9>. PMID: 33500742; PMCID: PMC7809919.
- Tamari, M. (1990). Ethical issues in bankruptcy: A Jewish perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 9, 785–789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00383276>
- Tasi, R. & Syamsir, S. (2020). Strengthening Work Ethics and Integrity in Corruption Prevention. Conference Proceedings of the 1st Tidar International Conference on Advancing Local Wisdom Towards Global Megatrends, TIC 2020, 21-22 October 2020, Magelang, Jawa Tengah, Indonesia. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356533032_Strengthening_Work_Ethics_and_Integrity_in_Corruption_Prevention. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.21-10-2020.2311842>
- Ud Din, M., Khan, F., Khan, U., Kadarningsih, A., & Darmi, S. (2019). The Effect of Islamic Work Ethics on the Job Performance: Mediating Role of Intrinsic Motivation. *International Journal of Islamic Business Ethics* 4(2), 676.

<https://doi.org/10.30659/ijibe.4.2.676-688>

Udin, U., Dananjoyo, R., Shaikh, M., & Vio Linarta, D. (2022). Islamic Work Ethics, Affective Commitment, and Employee's Performance in Family Business: Testing Their Relationships. *SAGE Open*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221085263>

Van Ness, R.K., Melinsky, K., Buff, C. & Seifert, C.F. (2010). Work Ethic: Do New Employees Mean New Work Values? *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 22 (1), 10-34.

Whitton, H. (2021). Implementing Effective Ethics Standards in Government and Civil Service. *Transparency International*. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/mena/governance/35521740.pdf>

Wilkinson, D. (2000). *The Researcher's Toolkit: The Complete Guide to Practitioner Research*. London: Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203185124>

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